

THE ϕ -SCALE OF POTENTIAL AND ITS APPLICATION TO SOME
ELECTROCHEMICAL PROBLEMS. PART I. THE NULL-
POINTS OF METALS AND THE DEFINITION OF
THE ϕ -SCALE OF POTENTIALS

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A brief summary of the methods for the determination of the values of zero charge potentials of metals ($\epsilon_{q=0}$) has been given. The most reliable values of $\epsilon_{q=0}$ have been collected and tabulated. The scale of ϕ -potential has been described, in which every value of potential (ϕ) is given in relation to the corresponding value of $\epsilon_{q=0}$. The physical meaning of the ϕ -potential and its relation to the charge of metal, to the structure of electrical double layer and to the ion-exchange current have been considered.

At the beginning of this century it was shown that the maximum of electrocapillary curve corresponded to the uncharged surface of metal. The assumption was made that in this case the potential of mercury related to the solution was also equal to zero, and the dropping mercury electrode was therefore chosen as a base for the so-called "absolute potentials" of metals. The values of these "absolute potentials" were tabulated and given in many reference books. It was Frumkin who proved the invalidity of this proposition. Frumkin* and his school used to refer to the potential of the maximum of electrocapillary curve as "the potential of zero charges of metal ($\epsilon_{q=0}$)", or as a "null-point of metal". At present there are several methods for determining $\epsilon_{q=0}$ -values, which have been elaborated by many investigators, and especially by Frumkin and his collaborators.

In this paper it is impossible to go into detailed consideration of these methods but it is quite necessary to discuss them in brief.

(i). *The Method of Electrocapillary Curves**.—In this method the null-point of metal is identified with the potential at the maximum of electrocapillary curve, obtained in a solution devoid of any surface-active particles. This method is applicable in the case of liquid metals such as mercury, gallium, amalgams**, and it has been successfully used also in estimating the null-points of different molten metals in contact with molten salts (Karpachew *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem. USSR.*, 1936, 7, 754; 1937, 10, 739; 1944, 17, 47; 1948, 22, 521, 1949, 28, 453; *Acta Physicochim.*, 1940, 12, 583; 1942, 16, 331; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, A176, 182).

(ii). *The Method of Contact Angle*.—In this method the null-point of metal is estimated by measuring the contact angle (θ) between the gas or oil bubble and the metal, both immersed in the same solution, and by plotting the values of θ against the potential of the metal (Möller, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1908, 68, 226; Frumkin *et al.*,

*For bibliography see: Frumkin, *Ergebn. exact. Naturweiss.*, 1928, 7, 235, and Parsons in Bockris-Conway, "Modern Aspects of Electro-chemistry", 1954, London.

** The modification of this method in which the surface tension is calculated from the weight of given number of drops was used for determining the $\epsilon_{q=0}$ -values of unstable amalgams (Antropov *et al.*, *Trans. Novolcherkassk Polytech. Inst.*, 1956, 34/48, 63, 69).

Phys. Z. Sowjet., 1932, 1, 225; 1934, 5, 418; *Actualities Sci. Industr.*, Paris, 1937, N373; Ukshe and Levin, *Compt. rend. Acad. Sci. USSR.*, 1955, 105, 113). This method is applicable to metals with clean and smooth surface.

(iii). *The Surface Hardness Method.*—In this method the value of $\epsilon_{q=0}$ is identified with the potential corresponding to the extremum on surface hardness or external friction-potential curves (Rehbinder and Venstrom, *Acta Physicochim.*, 1944, 19, 36; *Compt. rend. Acad. Sci. USSR.*, 1949, 68, 325; *J. Phys. Chem. USSR.*, 1952, 26, 12; Lücke and Mazing, *Z. Metallkunde*, 1951, 42, 361; Bokris and Parry-Jones, *Nature*, 1953, 171, 930). This method is applicable to solid metals.

(iv). *The Adsorption Method.*—In this method the null-point of metal corresponds to the value of potential at which there is no superfluous adsorption of acidic or alkaline compounds from the solution (Shlygin, Frumkin and Medvedovsky, *Acta Physicochim.*, 1936, 4, 911; Frumkin and Shlygin, *ibid.*, 1936, 5, 819; Kutchinsky, Barstein and Frumkin, *ibid.*, 1940, 12, 795; Veselovsky, *ibid.*, 1939, 11, 815). This method is especially useful in case of metals with a large specific surface.

(v). *Surface Charge Method.*—In this method it is assumed that the null-point of metal is equal to the potential at which the formation of a new area does not require any quantity of electricity for keeping the potential constant (Frumkin, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, 108, 55; Bennewitz, *ibid.*, 1926, 124, 115; Frumkin and Cirves, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 74; Grahame *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2978; 1952, 74, 1207). This method is applicable to liquid metals, but it can also be useful for the investigation of solid metals.

(vi). *The Electric Capacity Method.*—In this method the $\epsilon_{q=0}$ value is found from the position of the minimum on the curve: double layer capacity-potential (Proskurniu and Vorsina, *Compt. rend. Acad. Sci. USSR.*, 1939, 24, 915; Vorsina and Frumkin, *ibid.*, 1939, 24, 518; Borisova, Ershler and Frumkin, *J. Phys. Chem. USSR.*, 1948, 22, 925; Borisova and Ershler, *ibid.*, 1950, 24, 337). This method is applicable to different metals irrespective of their states.

(vii). *The Polarisation Curves Method.*—In this method the null-point of metal is associated with the bend of polarisation curve, which is due to the change of sign of the electrode surface (Lukovtcev, Levina and Frumkin, *J. Phys. Chem. USSR.*, 1939, 13, 916; Kolotyркиn and Bune, *ibid.*, 1947, 21, 581; Kolotyркиn and Medvedeva, *ibid.*, 1951, 25, 1355; Antropov and Listopodov, *Trans. Novotcherkassk Polytech. Inst.*, 1956, 34/48, 87). This method can only give approximate values of $\epsilon_{q=0}$, shifted usually in the negative direction. It is only applicable when the overvoltage is connected with slow discharge of hydrogen ions or of some other charged particles.

(viii). *The Work Function Method.*—In this method the value of $\epsilon_{q=0}$ is calculated from the corresponding value of work function (ϕ_e) by means of the semi-empirical equation

$$\epsilon_{q=0} = a - b\phi_e \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where a and b are empirical constants (Vaseniū, *J. Phys. Chem. USSR.*, 1953, 27, 878). Equation (1) is based on the assumption of a simple relation existing between the

difference of null-points of two metals and their Volta-potential (Frumkin and Gorodetskaja, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 130, 451).

With the methods (iv), (v) and (vi), the most reliable values of $\epsilon_{q=0}$ can be obtained. But while using the method (vi), it is necessary to consider that the values of $\epsilon_{q=0}$ found for solid metals will be sufficiently accurate only when the surfaces of the metals are smooth and homogeneous.

Fairly accurate data have been obtained for many molten metals by means of method (iv). It will be of interest to compare these data with the values of $\epsilon_{q=0}$ obtained for aqueous solutions. The results of this comparison are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Comparison of $\epsilon_{q=0}$ -values by different methods and under varied conditions.

Metal.	Electrolyte.	Temp.	Method.	$\epsilon_{q=0}$.
Tl	A*	420°	(i)	-0.74 volt
Tl	10 ⁻³ N-KCl	20°	(vi)	-0.82
Tl	1N-Na ₂ SO ₄	20°	(iii)	-0.69
Cd	A*	450°	(i)	-0.72
Cd	5 × 10 ⁻³ N-KCl	20°	(vi)	-0.90
Cd	" "	20°	(iii)	-0.70
Pb	A*	450°	(i)	-0.66
Pb	—	—	—	-0.64
Zn	A*	450°	(i)	-0.62
Zn	1N-Na ₂ SO ₄	20°	(iii)	-0.49
Ga	A*	450°	(i)	-0.60
Ga	1N-KCl, 0.1-N HCl	40°	(i)	-0.19
Mg	Solutions, melts	—	Diff. methods	-0.21
Ag	A*	1050°	(i)	-0.49
Ag	0.1N-KNO ₃	20°	(iv)	-0.05
Te	A*	550°	(i)	-0.59
Te	1N-Na ₂ SO ₄	20°	(iii)	-0.60

*By A is indicated the eutectic mixture of LiCl and KCl.

It is evident that the values of $\epsilon_{q=0}$ obtained by different methods are in fair agreement. By comparing the $\epsilon_{q=0}$ -values for aqueous solutions and for molten salts, an assumption has been made (Antropov, *Trans Novotcherkassk Polytech. Inst.*, 1954, 25/39, 5) that the null-point of mercury does not depend on the nature of the solvent and does not change with temperature. The validity of this assumption follows from Table I where all the values of $\epsilon_{q=0}$, except those for silver, are approximately the same in molten salts and in aqueous solutions. It means that the role of adsorption of polar water molecules is of no great importance. The data obtained in molten salts can therefore be used for aqueous solutions, and *vice versa*. The sudden variation of the value of $\epsilon_{q=0}$ for silver is presumably due to interaction between silver and molten halide salts.

The results obtained by means of method (viii) and some other methods have not been included in Table I. Although the method (viii) offers a possibility of calculating $\epsilon_{q=0}$ for nearly all metals, this method is not sufficiently reliable in view of the fact

that most of the values of φ_e as obtained at present are far from being highly accurate. This method therefore can only be used in those cases where there are no experimental data available.

Some of the values of $\epsilon_{q=0}$, as estimated by the above methods, are collected in Table II. The majority of them are average or the most reliable experimental quantities. For ferrous metals, only the $\epsilon_{q=0}$ values were calculated by means of the equation (Antropov, *Uspechy Khimii, USSR.*, 1956, 25, 1043):

$$\epsilon_{q=0} = -4.21 + 0.88\varphi_e \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

the most accurate data being used for φ_e (Tsarcv, "Contact Potentials", USSR., 1949; Sachtler, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1955, 59, 119).

TABLE II
List of null-points of metals.*

Metal ...	Na/Hg**	Tl	Cd	Pb	Zn	Ga
$\epsilon_{q=0}$ (volts) ...	-1.79	-0.82	-0.72	-0.67	-0.64	-0.60
Metal ..	Co	Cr	Zn/Hg **	Al	Tl/Hg **	Sn
$\epsilon_{q=0}$ (volts) ...	-0.51	-0.45	-0.46	-0.40	-0.36	-0.34
Metal ...	Cd/Hg **	Hg	Cu/Hg **	Hg	Fe	Cu
$\epsilon_{q=0}$ (volts) ...	-0.34	-0.19	-0.18	-0.05	0.02	+0.10
Metal ...	C _{act} Ni	Pt/H	Te	Pt/O		
$\epsilon_{q=0}$ (volts) ...	+0.20, +0.21	+0.25	+0.60	~1.0		

*The list of values for several metals has also been given by Frumkin (*J. Phys. Chem. USSR.*, 1934, 5, 240), by Parsons (*loc. cit.*) and by Antropov (*loc. cit.*).

**The data correspond to 0.01 in terms of the molar fraction of metal in amalgam. Within certain limits of concentration, the relation of $\epsilon_{q=0}$ of amalgams to their composition can be given by equation,

$$x/n\epsilon_{q=0} = \text{const} \pm 5 \log N_{Me} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

(see Smirnova, Smirnov and Antropov, *Trans. Novotcherkassk Polytech. Inst.*, 1936, 24/18, 69).

The potentials used by electrochemists are generally given against some reference electrode, very often *versus* normal hydrogen electrode (hydrogen scale of potentials). All the values of $\epsilon_{q=0}$ in Table II are also given in hydrogen scale (ϵ -scale). This scale, though very useful in thermodynamical treatment of electrochemical system, is at the same time not so convenient in solving the kinetics problems of electrochemistry. The hydrogen scale as well as other scales, based on some reference electrode, cannot give any information regarding the change of the metal in relation to the solution. The value and the sign of the ϵ -potential show only the relation of the electrode under investigation to the reference electrode. The fact that the ϵ -potentials of different metals in equilibrium with solutions of their salts are equal, does not mean that the charges of these two metals are the same; it only indicates that they are in equilibrium with one another.

In many cases another scale, in which the null-point of metal is chosen as the basis, is more suitable (Antropov, *J. Phys. Chem. USSR.*, 1951, 25, 1494). It is

obvious that in this scale each value of potential (φ) represents a difference between the potential of the electrode under given conditions and the corresponding value of $e_{q=0}$. Thus, the standard potential of the metal in this new scale will be:

$${}_M\varphi^0 = {}_M e^0 - {}_M e_{q=0} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

For example:

$${}_{Zn}\varphi^0 = {}_{Zn} e^0 - {}_{Zn} e_{q=0} = -0.76 - (-0.64) = -0.12V \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

To elucidate the physical meaning of the potential in this scale, hereafter indicated as φ -scale, consider the system: $M/S/M'/M''$.

The E.M.F. (E) of this system will be given by the formula:

$$E = {}^M\Delta^{M''}\varphi + {}^M\Delta^S\varphi + {}^M\Delta^{M'}\varphi \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

where φ 's are the values of so-called inner potentials of corresponding phases (Lange, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1951, 55, 26; Parsons, *loc. cit.*).

The ${}^M\Delta^{M'}\varphi$, *i. e.*, the difference of inner potentials of two metals M and M' , is equal to the Galvani potential. The ${}^M\Delta^S\varphi$ is the difference of inner potentials of metal M and solution S . On the other hand,

$${}^M\Delta^S\varphi = {}^M g_{ion}^S + {}^M g_{dip}^S \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where g_{ion} is a result of the ionic transition through the metal—solution interface and g_{dip} is due to the oriented adsorption of polar molecules at the same interface. A similar equation will be valid for ${}^M\Delta^{M'}\varphi$, hence,

$$E = {}^M\Delta^{M''}\varphi + {}^M g_{ion}^S + {}^M g_{dip}^S + {}^M g_{dip}^{M'} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

It will be assumed that the E.M.F. of this system is equivalent to φ -potential of metal M' , *i. e.*

$$E = {}^{M'}\varphi \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

But in this case all the three metals M , M' and M'' are of the same nature and composition and, hence, the ${}^M\Delta^{M'}\varphi$ will be equal to zero. Moreover, one of the two samples of the same metal placed under conditions corresponding to a potential equals to the null-point of this metal; therefore ${}^M g_{ion}^S$ will also be equal to zero, and

$${}^{M'}\varphi = {}^M g_{ion}^{M'} + {}^M g_{dip}^{M'} - {}^M g_{dip}^M \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

It means that the potential of a metal, given in φ -scale, is a measure of its charge and of the change of character and degree of dipoles orientation on the metal—solution interface. From equation (10) it is evident that ${}^{M'}\varphi$ can be equal to zero in two cases: (1) when the value of ${}^M g_{ion}^{M'}$ is equal to zero and ${}^M g_{dip}^{M'}$ is equal to ${}^M g_{dip}^M$; this corresponds to the conception of null-point of metal which is used in this paper; (2) when the value of ${}^M g_{ion}^{M'}$ is compensated for by the difference (${}^M g_{dip}^{M'} - {}^M g_{dip}^M$). These

conclusions are of some interest in connection with the discussion on Lippmann's and Billitzer's potentials (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1955, 59, 818). It is also evident that the value and the sign of φ -potential stand in close relation to the structure of electrical double layer on the metal—solution interface. This is shown in Fig. 1 which

gives a somewhat simplified picture of the double layer for the two cases: (a) $\varphi > 0$ and (b) $\varphi < 0$. As is seen from Fig. 1, if $\varphi < 0$, the discharge and the ionisation of metallic ions in the presence of foreign cations will be retarded due to the adsorption of the latter on the metal-solution interface. On the contrary, when $\varphi > 0$, the adsorption of anions will accelerate the process of ion exchange between these two phases. Therefore, the exchange current corresponding to the equilibrium state of metal-solution system ought to have some functional connection with φ -potential.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

There are very few experimental data to prove this suggestion, but Fig. 2 corroborates it. In drawing this picture we have used the values of exchange currents obtained by Randles and Somerton (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1952, 48, 951) for dilute amalgams in contact with solutions containing the salt of the corresponding metal and an excess of foreign electrolyte*. The values of $i_{q=0}$ were calculated on the strength of the supposition that the concentration of metal atoms in amalgams was the same ($1 \times 10^{-3} N$) as that of metal ions in the solution, the data for $i_{q=0}$ being those obtained by Smirnova, Smirnov and Antropov (*loc. cit.*). The value of the velocity of ion exchange for mercury was taken from a paper by Rosental and Ershler (*J. Phys. Chem. USSR.*, 1948, 22, 1944).

It is therefore natural to expect that the value of φ -potential should play an important role in all rate electrochemical processes. Other papers of this series will be devoted to this problem.

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*The data for Bi have not been included in Fig. 2 because we have no values of $i_{q=0}$ that may be relied upon.